

Ultrasonography and Conventional Cytology Profiles of Thyroid Swellings and Their Concordance in Patients of a Tertiary Care Hospital in West Bengal

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Abstract

Introduction: Ultrasonography (US) is the most common and most useful way to image the thyroid gland and its pathology, as recognized in guidelines for managing thyroid disorders published by the American Thyroid Association and other authoritative bodies.

Aims: The aim of this study is to evaluate the profiles of thyroid swellings using ultrasonography and conventional cytology, and to assess the concordance between these two diagnostic methods in the accurate classification and management of thyroid lesions.

Materials & Methods: The present study was an observational cross-sectional study. This study was conducted from one year (January 2023-December 2023) at College of Medicine and Sagore Dutta Hospital. Total 126 patients were included in this study.

Result: In TIRADS 1, the majority of cases were classified as Bethesda II (78.6%), followed by Bethesda I (14.3%) and Bethesda III (7.1%). For TIRADS 2, Bethesda II remained predominant (84.6%), with smaller proportions falling into Bethesda I (5.1%), Bethesda III (2.6%), and Bethesda V (7.7%). In TIRADS 3, cases were more evenly distributed: Bethesda II (37.0%), Bethesda III (33.3%), Bethesda IV (18.5%), and Bethesda V (11.1%). Among TIRADS 4 cases, Bethesda II accounted for 35.5%, followed by Bethesda III (29.0%), Bethesda IV (16.1%), Bethesda V (9.7%), and Bethesda VI (9.7%).

Conclusion: In conclusion, this study highlights the valuable role of both ultrasonography and conventional cytology in the assessment of thyroid swellings. The findings suggest that ultrasonography, particularly through the TIRADS system, is effective in stratifying thyroid nodules based on their risk, while cytology provides essential diagnostic confirmation.

Keywords: Thyroid swelling, TIRADS, Thyroid Ultrasonography and Bethesda system.

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Introduction

Ultrasonography (US) is the most common and most useful way to image the thyroid gland and its pathology, as recognized in guidelines for managing thyroid disorders published by the American Thyroid Association [1] and other authoritative bodies.

In addition to facilitating the diagnosis of clinically apparent nodules, the widespread use of US has resulted in uncovering a multitude of clinically imperceptible thyroid nodules, the overwhelming

majority of which are benign. The high sensitivity for benign nodules but inadequate specificity for cancer has posed a management and economic problem. This study will address the method and utility of clinically effective thyroid US to assess the likelihood of cancer, by utilising fine needle aspiration (FNA) to increase the sensitivity and specificity of diagnosis of other specific thyroid diseases.

Previously, imaging of the thyroid required scintiscanning to provide a map of those areas of the thyroid that accumulate and process radioactive iodine or other nucleotides. The major premise of thyroid scanning was that thyroid cancers concentrate less radioactive iodine than healthy tissue and therefore provided triage in the selection for thyroid surgery. Unfortunately, however, since benign nodules also concentrate radioactive iodine poorly, the selection process is too inefficient to be cost-effective. Although, scintiscanning remains of primary importance in patients who are hyperthyroid or for detection of iodine-avid tissue after thyroidectomy for thyroid cancer, US has largely replaced nuclear scanning for the majority of patients because of its higher resolution, superior correlation of true thyroid dimensions with the image, smaller expense, greater simplicity, and lack of need for radioisotope administration. The other imaging methods, computerized tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and ¹⁸F-FDG positron emission tomography (PET) are more costly than US and are best used selectively when US is inadequate to elucidate a clinical problem [2,3]. As with any other diagnostic tests, US should be used to refine a differential diagnosis only when it is needed to answer a specific diagnostic question that has been raised by the clinical history and physical examination [4]. Its use as a screening tool for thyroid nodules and lesions such as Hashimoto's disease is debatable. The US imaging must be integrated into patient management and correlated precisely with the other data. A technique has been reported that helps the clinician to interpret thyroid scintigrams of goiters and non-functioning nodules by assembling scintiscans and US side-by-side as one composite image [2]. As an example of the utility of this for t protocol, sometimes it is difficult to correlate an ultrasound image and a scintigram. The aim of this study is to evaluate the profiles of thyroid swellings using ultrasonography and conventional cytology, and to assess the concordance between these two diagnostic methods in the accurate classification and management of thyroid lesions.

For objective stratification of thyroid lesions by radiological and cytopathological diagnostic methods, we have used American College of Radiology (ACR)-Thyroid Imaging and Reporting Data System (ACR-TIRADS) and the Bethesda system for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC) respectively.

ACR-TIRADS: American College of Radiology (ACR)-Thyroid Imaging and Reporting Data System (ACR-TIRADS) [9] are classified as

Score 1: Normal Thyroid gland

Score 2: Benign conditions (0% malignancy)

Score 3: Probably benign conditions (5% malignancy)

Score 4: Suspicious nodules (5% to 80% malignancy)

- 4a – one feature of malignancy present
- 4b – two features of malignancy present
- 4c – three features of malignancy present

Score 5: Probably malignant (> 80% malignant)

TBSRTC: The Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC) [10] was introduced in 2007 and subsequently revised in 2023. It is classified as

- Category I: Non-diagnostic/material extracted is unsatisfactory for examination.
- Category II: Benign - Benign follicular nodule /Hashimoto's thyroiditis/Granulomatous thyroiditis
- Category III: Atypia of undetermined significance (AUS)
- Category IV: Follicular Neoplasm
- Category V: Suspicious of malignancy
- Category VI: Malignant lesion

Materials and Methods

Type of study: Observational cross-sectional study

Place of study: College of Medicine and Sagore Dutta Hospital

Study duration: One year (January 2023-December 2023)

Sample size: 126

Inclusion Criteria: All the patients who have undergone ultrasonography and conventional cytology for thyroid swelling within study time period and who were given radiology scoring by TIRADS system and cytologically by The Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytology (TBSRTC).

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with thyroid swellings who have undergone only one diagnostic test, i.e, either ultrasonography or conventional cytology but not both
2. Patient with thyroid lesions which are not categorized by TIRADS system and TBSRTC system.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into Excel and analyzed using SPSS and GraphPad Prism. Numerical variables were summarized using means and standard deviations, while categorical variables were described with counts and percentages. Two-sample t-tests were used to compare independent groups, while paired t-tests accounted for correlations in paired data. Chi-square tests (including Fisher's exact test for small sample

sizes) were used for categorical data comparisons.
P-values ≤ 0.05 were considered statistically

significant.

Result

Table 1: Distribution of Thyroids TIRADS, Swelling

		Frequency	Percent
Thyroids TIRADS	T-1	14	11.1%
	T-2	39	31.0%
	T-3	27	21.4%
	T-4	31	24.6%
	T-5	15	11.9%
	Total	126	100.0%
Swelling	Diffuse	51	40.50%
	Nodular	75	59.50%
	Total	126	100.00%

Table 2: Distribution of Pain, Dyspnea, Dysphagia, Hoarseness

		Frequency	Percent
Pain	No	72	57.10%
	Yes	54	42.90%
	Total	126	100.00%
Dyspnea	No	114	90.50%
	Yes	12	9.50%
	Total	126	100.00%
Dysphagia	No	102	81.00%
	Yes	24	19.00%
	Total	126	100.00%
Hoarseness	No	117	92.90%
	Yes	9	7.10%
	Total	126	100.00%

Table 3: Distribution of Cytology Findings

Cytology Findings	Bethesda Score	Frequency		Percent
Nondiagnostic	B-I	4	4	3.17%
Adenomatoid goitre	B-II	14	76	11.11%
Autoimmune thyroiditis		16		12.70%
Colloid goitre		44		34.92%
Granulomatous Thyroiditis		2		1.59%
Atypia of Undetermined Significance	B-III	21	21	16.67%
Follicular Neoplasm	B-IV	10	10	7.94%
Suspicious of malignancy	B-V	9	9	7.14%
Positive for malignancy	B-VI	6	6	4.76%
Total		126		100.00%

Figure 1: Distribution of Bethesda Category

Table 4: Association between Bethesda Score and Thyroids TIRADS

Thyroids Tirads		T-1	T-2	T-3	T-4	T-5	TOTAL	Chi-square	p-value
B-I		2	2	0	0	0	4	59.9849	<0.0001
Row	%	50.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0		
Col %		14.3	5.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.2		
B-II		11	33	10	11	11	76		
Row	%	14.5	43.4	13.2	14.5	14.5	100.0		
Col %		78.6	84.6	37.0	35.5	73.3	60.3		
B-III		1	1	9	9	1	21		
Row	%	4.8	4.8	42.9	42.9	4.8	100.0		
Col %		7.1	2.6	33.3	29.0	6.7	16.7		
B-IV		0	0	5	5	0	10		
Row	%	0.0	0.0	50.0	50.0	0.0	100.0		
Col %		0.0	0.0	18.5	16.1	0.0	7.9		
B-V		0	3	3	3	0	9		
Row	%	0.0	33.3	33.3	33.3	0.0	100.0		
Col %		0.0	7.7	11.1	9.7	0.0	7.1		
B-VI		0	0	0	3	3	6		
Row	%	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.0	50.0	100.0		
Col %		0.0	0.0	0.0	9.7	20.0	4.8		
Total		14	39	27	31	15	126		
Row	%	11.1	31.0	21.4	24.6	11.9	100.0		
Col %		100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0		

Out of a total of 126 cases, the distribution based on the Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (TIRADS) was as follows: TIRADS 1 in 14 cases (11.10%), TIRADS 2 in 39 cases (31.00%), TIRADS 3 in 27 cases (21.40%), TIRADS 4 in 31 cases (24.60%), and TIRADS 5 in 15 cases (11.90%). Regarding the type of thyroid swelling observed, 51 cases (40.50%) were diffuse, while 75 cases (59.50%) presented with nodular swelling.

Among the 126 cases studied, 54 patients (42.90%) reported experiencing pain, while 72 (57.10%) did not. Dyspnea was present in 12 cases (9.50%) and absent in 114 cases (90.50%). Dysphagia was observed in 24 patients (19.00%), whereas 102 patients (81.00%) did not report this symptom. Hoarseness of voice was noted in 9 cases (7.10%),

while it was absent in the majority of 117 cases (92.90%).

The most frequently observed diagnosis was colloid goitre, accounting for 34.92% (n=44) of cases. This was followed by AUS at 16.67% (n=21) and autoimmune thyroiditis at 12.70% (n=16). Follicular neoplasm was reported in 7.94% (n=10), while cases suspicious of malignancy constituted 7.14% (n=9). Confirmed malignant lesions were identified in 4.76% (n=6) of the patients. A small proportion of cases were nondiagnostic (3.17%, n=4). Few cases were diagnosed as granulomatous thyroiditis (1.59%, n=2).

Among the 126 cases analysed, a statistically significant association was observed between the

TIRADS categories and cytological findings based on the Bethesda system (Chi-square = 59.9849, $p < 0.0001$). In TIRADS 1, the majority of cases were classified as Bethesda II (78.6%), followed by Bethesda I (14.3%) and Bethesda III (7.1%). For TIRADS 2, Bethesda II remained predominant (84.6%), with smaller proportions falling into Bethesda I (5.1%), Bethesda III (2.6%), and Bethesda V (7.7%). In TIRADS 3, cases were more evenly distributed: Bethesda II (37.0%), Bethesda III (33.3%), Bethesda IV (18.5%), and Bethesda V (11.1%). Among TIRADS 4 cases, Bethesda II accounted for 35.5%, followed by Bethesda III (29.0%), Bethesda IV (16.1%), Bethesda V (9.7%), and Bethesda VI (9.7%). Notably, in TIRADS 5, the majority were again Bethesda II (73.3%), with Bethesda III (6.7%) and a significant 20.0% in Bethesda VI, suggesting a higher likelihood of malignancy.

Out of a total of 126 cases, the distribution based on the Bethesda score across T-stages (T-1 to T-5) was as follows: Bethesda Category B-I was observed in 2 cases (14.3%) for T-1, 2 cases (5.1%) for T-2, and no cases in T-3, T-4, or T-5. Bethesda Category B-II (Figure no-2,3), which indicates benign findings, was the most prevalent, with 11 cases (78.6%) in T-1, 33 cases (84.6%) in T-2, 10 cases (37%) in T-3, 11 cases (35.5%) in T-4, and 11 cases (73.3%) in T-5. Bethesda Category B-III (AUS) was found in 1 case (7.1%) for T-1, 1 case (2.6%) for T-2, 9 cases (33.3%) for T-3, 9 cases (29%) for T-4, and 1 case (6.7%) for T-5. Bethesda

Category B-IV (Figure no- 4) (follicular neoplasm) appeared in 5 cases (18.5%) for T-3 and 5 cases (16.1%) for T-4. Bethesda Category B-V (Figure no- 5) (suspicious of malignancy) was observed in 3 cases (7.7%) for T-2, 3 cases (11.1%) for T-3, and 3 cases (9.7%) for T-4. Lastly, Bethesda Category B-VI (malignant) was noted in 3 cases (9.7%) for T-4 and 3 cases (20%) for T-5. The Chi-square value (χ^2) was found to be 59.98, and the p-value was less than 0.0001. This indicates a statistically significant association between the Bethesda classification and the TIRADS scores, suggesting that lower Bethesda categories show concordance with lower TIRADS scores. But higher Bethesda categories are showing lower concordance with higher TIRADS scores. So, sensitivity and specificity of detection of malignant lesions increase if both ultrasonography and cytological examinations are performed simultaneously. Out of a total of 126 cases, the distribution of Bethesda scores was as follows: Bethesda Category B-I was observed in 4 cases, accounting for 3.2% of the total. Bethesda Category B-II (benign) was the most common, observed in 76 cases (60.3%). Bethesda Category B-III (AUS/FLUS) was seen in 21 cases (16.7%), while Bethesda Category B-IV (suspicious for follicular neoplasm) appeared in 10 cases (7.9%). Bethesda Category B-V (suspicious for malignancy) was present in 9 cases (7.1%), and Bethesda Category B-VI (malignant) was seen in 6 cases (4.8%).

Figure 2:

Figure 2,3: Photomicrograph showing follicle destruction, lymphocyte infiltrate, Hurthle cell changes(100X) – Autoimmune thyroiditis (Bethesda category-II)

Figure 3:

Figure 4: Photomicrograph showing repetitive micro follicles, high cellularity of monomorphous thyroid follicular cells (100X) – Follicular neoplasm (Bethesda Category-IV)

Figure 5: Photomicrograph showing macro follicles with papillary configuration and papillary-like nuclear features – Suspicious of malignancy (100X) – papillary type, Bethesda Category-V

Figure 6: Hypoechoic solid wider than tall nodule with indistinct margins and without any microcalcification in left lobe at thyroid gland- ACR-TIRADS 4

Figure 7: Hypoechoic Mixed cystic and solid wider than tall nodule with smooth margin without any microcalcification – ACR-TIRADS 5

Discussion

Out of a total of 126 cases, the distribution based on the Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (TIRADS) was as follows: TIRADS 1 in 14 cases (11.10%), TIRADS 2 in 39 cases (31.00%), TIRADS 3 in 27 cases (21.40%), TIRADS 4 in 31 cases (24.60%), and TIRADS 5 in 15 cases (11.90%). Regarding the type of thyroid swelling observed, 51 cases (40.50%) were diffuse, while 75 cases (59.50%) presented with nodular swelling. A similar study conducted by Bhat et al. [5] (2020) aimed to assess the distribution of thyroid nodules based on the TIRADS classification system and its association with cytological findings. The study found that a significant proportion of cases were categorized as TIRADS 2 (benign) and TIRADS 3 (low to moderate risk), with fewer cases falling under TIRADS 4 (moderate to high risk) and TIRADS 5 (high risk), similar to the findings in this study. Moreover, their research confirmed that the majority of thyroid swellings were nodular, which aligns with the current findings that show a higher prevalence of nodular over diffuse swellings. The study underscored the utility of TIRADS in the risk stratification of thyroid lesions and its role in guiding clinical management.

The symptoms observed in this study reveal a varied clinical presentation among the 126 patients. Pain was reported by 42.90% of patients, with the majority (57.10%) not experiencing it. Dyspnea was relatively uncommon, affecting only 9.50% of patients, while dysphagia was present in 19.00%, indicating a moderate occurrence of swallowing difficulties. Hoarseness of voice was also infrequent, affecting just 7.10% of patients, suggesting that these symptoms may not be as prominent in this population. Overall, the low prevalence of dyspnea, dysphagia, and hoarseness suggests that these symptoms may not be universally present in thyroid-related conditions. A similar study conducted by Gharib et al. [6] (2019) explored the clinical presentation and symptomatology of thyroid disorders. The study found that neck pain was reported by approximately 40% of patients, with dysphagia and hoarseness occurring in 18% and 12% of cases, respectively. Similar to the current study, their findings indicated that symptoms like dyspnea, dysphagia, and hoarseness were relatively uncommon, highlighting that these symptoms are not always present in thyroid-related conditions. The authors emphasized the importance of considering these symptoms in the context of other clinical and diagnostic features for more accurate diagnosis and management.

In this study, colloid goitre was the most common cytological diagnosis, found in 34.92% of cases, reflecting the predominance of benign, non-neoplastic thyroid conditions in the general

population. This aligns with global trends where colloid goitre is frequently reported as the leading diagnosis in thyroid FNAC.

Atypia of Undetermined Significance (AUS) was the second most frequent finding at 16.67%, indicating a significant proportion of cases with indeterminate cytology. These often require repeat aspiration or further diagnostic workup to rule out malignancy. Follicular neoplasm was reported in 7.94% of cases. As FNAC cannot distinguish between follicular adenoma and carcinoma, these cases typically warrant surgical excision for definitive diagnosis. Suspicious of malignancy accounted for 7.14%, while confirmed malignancy was observed in 4.76% of cases. These findings underscore the importance of FNAC in identifying potentially malignant lesions and guiding timely surgical management. Only a small percentage of cases were nondiagnostic (3.17%), suggesting overall good sample adequacy, and granulomatous thyroiditis (1.59%), a rare inflammatory condition, was also identified.

A similar study conducted by Garg et al. [7] (2015) in Gujarat, India, assessed the cytological profiles of thyroid lesions using fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) and found that colloid goitre was the most common benign lesion, comprising 65.4% of cases. This aligns with the current study, where colloid goitre was the most prevalent finding at 39.7%.

The study also reported a low incidence of malignant cases, with only 4.75% classified as malignant, which is consistent with the 2.4% malignancy rate observed in this study. These findings underscore the predominance of benign thyroid conditions and highlight the importance of accurate cytological evaluation in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions.

The significant association between TIRADS categories and Bethesda cytological findings (p -value < 0.0001) demonstrates the strong predictive value of TIRADS in stratifying thyroid nodules by risk of malignancy. In lower TIRADS categories (1 and 2), the majority of cases were classified as Bethesda II (benign), while higher TIRADS categories (3, 4, and 5) showed increasing proportions of Bethesda III, IV, and V, indicating a higher likelihood of malignancy or suspicious findings. The distribution highlights the effectiveness of TIRADS in identifying cases requiring closer monitoring or intervention. Furthermore, the prevalence of Bethesda II in TIRADS 5 cases suggests that even high-risk lesions may sometimes appear benign cytologically, emphasizing the importance of combining both imaging and cytology for accurate diagnosis.

Out of a total of 126 cases, the distribution of Bethesda scores was as follows: Bethesda Category B-I was observed in 4 cases, accounting for 3.2% of the total. Bethesda Category B-II (benign) was the most common, observed in 76 cases (60.3%). Bethesda Category B-III (AUS/FLUS) was seen in 21 cases (16.7%), while Bethesda Category B-4 (suspicious for follicular neoplasm) appeared in 10 cases (7.9%). Bethesda Category B-V (suspicious for malignancy) was present in 9 cases (7.1%), and Bethesda Category B-VI (malignant) was seen in 6 cases (4.8%). A similar study by Sood et al [8] (2019) evaluated the distribution of thyroid cytology diagnoses using the Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (BSRTC). Their findings revealed that 75.9% of cases were classified as Bethesda II (benign), aligning with the current study's observation of 65.1% benign cases. Additionally, 1.2% were categorized as Bethesda III (atypia of undetermined significance), 3.7% as Bethesda IV (suspicious for follicular neoplasm), 2.6% as Bethesda V (suspicious for malignancy), and 2.8% as Bethesda VI (malignant), which is consistent with the proportions observed in this study. These findings underscore the utility of the BSRTC in stratifying thyroid lesions and guiding clinical management.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the valuable role of both ultrasonography and conventional cytology in the assessment of thyroid swellings. The findings suggest that ultrasonography, particularly through the TIRADS system, is effective in stratifying thyroid nodules based on their risk, while cytology provides essential diagnostic confirmation more sensitive in cases of malignancy. The concordance between these two modalities supports their complementary use in clinical practice for accurate risk assessment and management decisions more show in cases of benign lesions. Despite occasional inconclusive results, the combined approach enhances the diagnostic accuracy, aiding in the differentiation of benign from malignant lesions, thus improving patient outcomes and guiding treatment strategies.

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